

DESCRIPTIVE CHARECTERISTICS OF FLIPPED LEARNING IN IMPLEMENTING TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14995480>

Abstract: *This article discusses one of the modern teaching method “Flipped learning” as an effective way to organize students’ autonomous learning and classroom activities. the article reviews the history of this innovative method, its charecteristics and learning opportunities that can be provided to the learners. Besides, it can be identified relationship of Bloom’s taxonomy in traditional classes and flipped learning.*

Key words: *Flipped learning, Inverted classroom, educational process, Bloom’s taxonomy, autonomous learning, classroom activities.*

“Flipped Learning” is one of the modes of blended learning that student studies didactic materials before the learning process or during autonomous learning (for example, by watching online lectures. There are several names for this pedagogical technology, which are also called “Inverted Classroom”, “Flipped Classroom”, “Classroom Flipp”, “Flipp Instructions”, and if we look at its history, it dates back to the 1990s. J. Baker first assigned students to master the lecture text as homework before giving a lecture, and called this technology “Inverted classroom”. By the 2000s, with the rapid development of the Internet, J. Bergman and A. Sams prepared and sent video lectures to students who could not attend lectures. Later, they began to effectively apply it to all students and used the terms “Flipped learning” and “Flipped classroom”. The reason why we preferred the term “Flipped learning” over “Flipped classroom” or “Inverted Classroom” in our research is that we took into account that this technology covers not only the classroom learning process, but also the independent learning process of students. We follow the classification given by J. Bergman, A. Sams, J. Overmeyer and B. Willis. “Flipped learning” is a new technological approach that encourages students to independently explore the main facts and concepts of the subject using various methods outside the classroom. These include reading course materials, completing online modules, and watching video lectures. “The academic learning process is supplemented with dynamic interactive tasks, which engage students in active academic learning,” says J. Bergman. Active academic learning is defined as the dynamic application of the knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired by a student in the process of independent learning to the interactive and practical application in the classroom [4,20-24].

Also, K. Clark notes that an important aspect of “flirted learning” is the development of students’ teamwork skills. “Flirted learning” is technologically very suitable for developing teamwork skills. K. Clarke emphasizes in his research that it is difficult to develop students’ critical and analytical teamwork skills in a traditional classroom [5, 685].

We define “Flipped learning” technology as active academic education, in which the student dynamically uses the knowledge acquired in the process of independent learning with the help of materials presented in the classroom to the level of skills and competence in the classroom, using real-life situations, interactive-practical support in collaboration, and the development of critical thinking. Active academic learning also leads to an increase in student-talk time and a decrease in teacher-talk time, which in turn helps to manage and control the student’s emotional state and the learning rate. In the process of active academic learning, student-teacher feedback serves as a very important factor in ensuring mutual communication.

N. Hamdan and P. McKnight emphasize that the “Flipped learning” technology consists of four foundations. According to them, F is a “flexible environment”, that is, where and when the student can organize independent learning and, unlike traditional lessons, the lesson process takes place in a noisy and discussion-rich environment; L is a “learning culture”, the use of a student-centered approach to learning, unlike teacher-centered learning in traditional lessons. As much as possible, the lesson process should help students delve deeper into the subject [6, 24]. I is “Intentional content”, that is, the theoretical material that the student needs to master in independent learning is determined based on the level of complexity and assimilation capabilities, and the use of various interactive technologies in the lesson process, including problem-based learning, mutual feedback, Socratic discussion, etc.; The last P is “Professional educators”, The need for qualified educators is becoming more important. Qualified educators are tasked not only with organizing lessons for students using interactive technologies, but also with re-establishing contact with students when necessary, monitoring them, and providing instructions to solve problems they encounter. Thus, in the “Flipped learning” technology, the creation of a flexible learning environment focused on the individual in the academic education process of students is defined as a very important factor, and the skill of qualified educators in determining the content of education and providing the necessary instructions based on the ability to predict and monitor the development of students is defined as a guarantee of the success of this technology.

While the above ideas are related to student self-directed learning, another group of scholars have compared traditional academic teaching methods with lessons taught using the “flipped learning” technology. For example, “Why minimal guidance during instruction does not work?” by R.A. Kirschner, J. Sweller, and R.E. Clark. In their scientific article, they express the following opinion: “The reason why students independently complete homework after traditional lessons is that they receive sufficient information and instructions during the lesson [5, 686]. It has been observed that if these presentations are not delivered adequately, or if there is some misunderstanding on the part of students, they will encounter difficulties in completing homework assignments, which may lead to students having incorrect information and retaining it in their long-term memory. Therefore, in our opinion, when using the “Flipped Learning” technology, students have the opportunity to apply the information received from independent learning exercises during the academic lesson process by performing various exercises, thereby gaining a deeper understanding of the topics. H. Ahmed uses Bloom’s taxonomy of cognitive levels in his scientific work to compare traditional lessons with lessons in which the “Flipped Learning” technology was applied. As is known, Bloom’s taxonomy of cognitive levels is based on a constructive approach, that is, each level serves to acquire the next level and is divided into 6 levels: remembering, understanding, applying, analyzing, evaluating, creating. In turn, these six levels are further divided into two general ones, namely the lower cognitive level (which includes the levels of remembering, understanding, applying) and the higher cognitive level (which includes the levels of analyzing, evaluating, creating) [2,443]. H. Ahmad analyzed in his research how these cognitive levels are reflected in traditional and “flipped learning” technology.

Picture 1. The reflection of Bloom’s taxonomy in traditional classes and Flipped learning

N.L. Antonov and A.V. Merenkov, as a result of their scientific research, express the following opinion: The use of the “Flipped learning” technology in the educational process is based on a constructive model and serves to improve the information and communicative competence of future specialists. Based on the opinion they expressed, they noted that the implementation of this modern technology in practice can be carried out in a three-stage process [3,239]:

Picture 2. The educational process of “Flipped learning”

In our opinion, electronic technologies are of great importance as a component of the “Flipped learning” technology. This, in turn, allows future professionals to watch recorded lectures using smartphones or other mobile devices. The recorded video lectures are placed on online learning platforms as a means of organizing online learning. This allows students to access the materials without having to download large files to their devices.

Based on the above process, it can be emphasized that the “Flipped Learning” technology is a quasi-subjective-subjective learning process that improves students’ independent learning. M.V. Shakurova, in her research, divides the learning process into two types: subjective-quasi-subjective and quasi-subjective-subjective. The

meaning of the term “quasi-subjective” is given by Shakurova as follows: quasisubjectivity is a characteristic feature of a person’s self-understanding activity, the types of activity of an object that reflect the personality in the imagination [7,94]. It is understood in the process of learning, the self-understanding activity of a student, that is, the reflection of the types of activity of a future professional.

In conclusion, while in subjective-quasi-subjective teaching, the teacher is supposed to work in the conditions set by the teacher, achieve the goal of the lesson, and ensure that the subject is understood and accepted by the students, in quasi-subjective-subjective teaching, the student takes an active role in the academic lesson process, narrows down the misunderstandings in the information the student has, and the teacher is required to eliminate them. We can conclude that this is a manifestation of unusual student-teacher collaboration.

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